

SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN BASED ON DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: In this thesis, there are opinions on the methodology of developing speech skills of students of preschool educational organizations. Also, attention is paid to the issues related to the development of speech in the cognitive process of the mental development of the child, where the main attention is paid to the issue of raising a healthy child in our country.

Key words: intuition, perception, attention, memory, speech, tendency, dualism, imagination and thinking.

Introduction:

Dialogic speech occurs in the family, in the circle of parents and siblings. He tries to ask for what he needs, starts communication. Conversations on pre-prepared topics, dramatization methods, dramatization games, and question-and-answer sessions are very useful for developing the speech of preschool children. It should be noted that for a child, an adult is the only means of finding answers to questions, a source of interesting impressions. As the child strives to enter into a dialogue with adults, to own things and toys, he needs to use words to achieve these goals, sometimes he himself takes the initiative and expresses an opinion. In the course of dialogue with the child, an adult corrects the child's shortcomings by transforming one-word thoughts into grammatically fully formed words. The child actively assimilates what he has learned and uses it in his speech. Therefore, the contribution of parents, siblings and educators in the development of preschool children's speech is great.

Methods and innovative technologies in speech development.

Speech development of pre-school children is an important part of the competence approach to education of children defined in the "First Step" State Curriculum. First of all, communicative competence, that is, the formation of the ability to use communication tools in different situations, is defined as the general important competences of a 6-7-year-old child. So, communication competence takes the main place among the game, knowledge and social competence of the students. Therefore, the development of the child's speech and the formation of communication skills is the main task in the content of each educational activity. Efficiency is high when a child acquires new knowledge based on games and didactic tools. That is, rather than simple reading of fiction,

implementation of activities with the use of innovative educational technologies ensures and accelerates the speech development process of each child, thereby helping to improve the quality of education. For this, it is necessary to develop new technologies for the development of preschool children's speech and actively use them in the process. Forming the speech of preschool children is an important and difficult task. Successfully solving this problem is necessary both for preparing children for the upcoming school and for comfortable communication with others. Pedagogues of our country and the CIS countries have conducted a number of researches on the development of children's speech.

Innovative technologies are new methods and methods of mutual educational relations between educators and students, which ensure effective achievement of pedagogical results. Such an educational environment includes educational methods, methods, and tools aimed at achieving a positive result due to dynamic changes in the child's personal development in modern conditions. It was at MTT that, recognizing the incomparable role of fiction in the process of speech development, we observed the high effectiveness of teaching fiction to children with the help of new technologies. The development of preschool children's speech is largely related to the correct solution of the following:

- didactic materials for the development of speech include regular speech of parents, educators, fairy tales, poems, songs, stories that are read or told to children;
- modern organization of education using didactic materials;
- to ensure children's active speech communication in educational games.
- Today, the educator of the preschool educational organization faces the following difficulties in forming children's speech skills:
 - identifying and developing the individual abilities of each child;
 - child activation in educational relations based on cooperation;
 - creating special game situations with children with hidden speech skills.

Conducted experience

Thus, we classify the practical advantages of introducing a work of art in an innovative way rather than reading it traditionally. Traditional educational activities for preschool children recognize that the teacher tells stories, reads, and memorizes through repetition. But experience shows that children repeat

the teacher's story with minor changes, the stories are only interpreted using poor words. Therefore, after reading the story, instead of retelling the story, the game "Find the place of the pictures" that requires the children to put the mixed pictures based on the story on the magnetic board according to their place, encourages the children to be in an active speech situation. In the process of finding pictures according to the sequence of events, they develop not only their speech, but also their attention, observation, and logical thinking.

Observing the composition of the story that they are creating activates the students and tries to describe it with new words. This activity protects children from boredom, if it is not possible to retell the story of the whole group, this method involves all children in the work process.

Especially when the educator changes his status from the role of the main performer to the level of an observer, it gives children freedom. The pedagogue's encouragement of performing children's behavior paves the way for speech activity. When choosing such innovative technologies, it is necessary to pay attention to the following requirements:

- not to teach technology, but to direct the development of children's communication skills, education of speech culture;
- organization of active speech practice in various activities for each child, taking into account his age and individual characteristics.

In modern practice, preschool education is implementing a number of problems that require the exit of preschool education. Recently, the number of children with speech disorders has increased significantly, quantitative and qualitative changes are observed in their development. According to teachers of school and kindergarten therapists, 58% of preschool children and 56% of first graders have persistence in speech development. It should also be noted that authoritative speech loses its importance, because there are other standards of speech by modern children (television advertising, modern cartoons, communication on social networks, etc.). The trend of the language development of the language of modern society is biantualism and polylingualism (bilingualism and polybinism). The level of speech development of a preschool teacher leads to the failure of the school, because

Summary.

The components of preschool speech are the components of speech and the components of mental functions that are the weakest in the new school environment, which requires their maximum mobilization. At the current stage, traditional learning methods are not effective and do not meet the modern

requirements of the state and society. In the conditions of innovation, after the minimum term, it is necessary to solve the number of new tasks in front of the teacher, it is necessary to use new methods and technologies. The use of modern educational technologies opens up new opportunities for education and training of preschoolers. Truly innovative technologies are initially built on a competency approach and focus on training outcomes for the learner's future.

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